

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Design of photocurable thiol-epoxy resins for the processing of vitrimers with vat photopolymerisation 3D printing

Szymon Gaca,^{1,2} Kurt Dietliker,³ Elisabeth Rossegger,¹ Sandra Schlögl^{1, 2*}

1. Polymer Competence Center Leoben GmbH, Sauraugasse 1, 8700 Leoben, Austria
2. Chair of Chemistry of Polymeric Materials, Montanuniversitaet Leoben, Otto Glöckel-Straße 2/IV, 8700 Leoben, Austria
3. SCD Dr. Sommerlade Chemistry Design GmbH, Rheinfeldener Straße 27, 79395 Neuenburg am Rhein, Germany

Email: sandra.schloegl@pccl.at

Figure S1. FTIR spectra and decrease of the characteristic thiol absorption band (2567 cm^{-1}) versus curing time: resin (a,b) ECC-2, (c,d) ECC-5 and (e,f) ECC-8. The samples were illuminated (405 nm light at 35 mW/cm^2) for four minutes and then measurements were taken every 5 min (at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Change of the characteristic peaks related to the PBG as obtained from the FTIR spectra of (g) ECC-2, (h) ECC-5 and (i) ECC-8. (j) Thiol conversion (as obtained from the FTIR data) versus curing time and catalyst content.

Figure S2. Photographs of the printed model objects. (a) Top view of the printed model object with component dimensions; (b) Test objects printed with different individual layer thicknesses and lamp power but with the same exposure time. (c) Object printed obtained by printing with a 100 μm layer thickness.

Figure S3. (a) DMA and (b) TGA curve as obtained for DLP 3D printed resin ECC-8.